

Egyptian Nationalism from 1919 to the Present
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Cairo Institute for Liberal Arts and Sciences
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Wednesday 17:30-20:00/ Thursday 10:00-12:30
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Course Description

How has Egypt been imagined as a modern nation-state? how did Egyptian intellectuals and the educated middle class draw borders of nationhood, including and excluding various groups in the process? and what changes did Egyptian nationalism undergo with the achievement of complete political independence from Britain at mid-century, and beyond?

In this course, we will analyze the nature of modern Egyptian nationalism throughout its different stages of development, from 1919 to the present, looking for ruptures and continuities in the ways in which the Egyptian nation and national identity were imagined and constructed. A historical perspective into the origins and developments of Egyptian nationalism will help us put today's perception of Egypt as a nation in context.

We will then analyze recent manifestations of Egyptian nationalism, and the ideologies that underlie mainstream discourses on nationhood and patriotism post January 25th. We will treat "Egyptianness" as a product of a constant work of construction and exclusion, and will inquire into the role of the state and different socio-economic interest groups in shaping this process.

Course Objectives

- To dissect together Egyptian patriotism as it has evolved throughout the twentieth century, analyzing the assumptions it rests on and their implications, using different texts and images. Students will be encouraged to bring to class textual and visual materials they wish to analyze, and to develop their commentaries in relation to readings and class discussions.
- To read about the different theories on the rise of nationalism, and how it is constantly shaped by state power and elite interests.
- To de-construct hegemonic nationalist discourses and understand their implications in terms of the processes of inclusion and exclusion they involve, and consequently to view nationalism and patriotism as time-specific constructions that may serve elite interests.

Course Schedule

Week 1, January 17/18

Introductions

Course Outline and expectations

What is nationalism?

Week 2, January 25/26

Theories of the Emergence of Nationalism

- Ernest Gellner, *Nations and Nationalism* (p.19-58)
- Benedict Anderson, *Imagined Communities* (p.37-46; 113-140)
- Eric Hobsbawm, *Nations and Nationalism since 1780* (p.80-130)
- Juan R. I. Cole and Deniz Kandiyoti, "Introduction," *International Journal of Middle East Studies*, Vol. 34, No. 2, Special Issue: Nationalism and the Colonial Legacy in the Middle East and Central Asia (May, 2002), p. 189-199

Week Three: February 1/2

1919-1936: Anti-Colonial Nationalist Mobilization, and Elite Definition of the Nation

- Israel Gershoni and James Jankowski, *Egypt, Islam and the Arabs: The Search for Egyptian Nationhood, 1900-1930*, until page 190 (or at least p.40-54; 77-95; 130-190 and 270-274).
- Ellis Goldberg, "Peasants in Revolt – Egypt 1919," *International Journal of Middle East Studies*, Vol. 24, No. 2 (May, 1992), pp. 261-280
- Zachary Lockman, "The Social Roots of Nationalism: Workers and the National Movement in Egypt, 1908-19," *Middle Eastern Studies*, Vol. 24, No. 4 (Oct., 1988), pp. 445-459
- عاصم الدسوقي، كبار ملاك الأراضي الزراعية و دورهم في المجتمع المصري (1914-1952)، ص 253-284
- Joel Beinin and Zachary Lockmann, *Workers on the Nile*, p.83-120 and p.154-170 (*Recommended: p.121-137).
- * Recommended: Tamim Barghouthi "The Case of Egypt: A National Liberation Movement and a Colonially Created Government," PhD Dissertation, p.36-45 and p.106-117

Week Four, February 8/9

The 1930s and 1940s: Nationalism of the Rising Effendiyya; Islam and Nationalism

- Israel Gershoni and James Jankowski, *Redefining the Egyptian Nation 1930-1945*, until page 142 (or at least p.1-34; 54-116)
- Partha Chatterjee, *The Nation and its Fragments* (p.3-13)

- Sami Zubaida, "Islam and Nationalism: Continuities and Contradictions," *Nations and Nationalism* 10 (4), 2004, 407–413. Accessible at <http://onlinelibrary.wiley.com/doi/10.1111/j.1354-5078.2004.00174.x/epdf>
- Eric Davis, "[The Concept of Revival and the Study of Islam in Politics](#)," *The Islamic Impulse*, 1987
- Charles D. Smith, "Hayat Muhammad and the Muslim Brothers: Two interpretations of Egyptian Islam and their Socio-economic Implications", *Journal of the American Research Center in Egypt*, Vol. 16 (1979), pp.175-181

Week Five, February 15/16

Convergences in Islamic and non-Islamic Nationalisms: Prelude to Nasserism

- شريف يونس، نداء الشعب: تاريخ نقدي للأيديولوجيا الناصرية، ص 715-657
- Rim Naguib, "Intelligentsia Class Formation and Ideologies in Peripheral Societies: Comparing Egypt and Iran, 1922-1952," PhD Dissertation, Chapter V-VI p.228-318
- * Recommended, Franz Fanon, *The Wretched of the Earth*, Chapter III, "The Trials and Tribulations of National Consciousness" p.97-144

Week Six, February 22/29

Nasserism and Nationalism under Nasser

The making of "the people," and the personification of the nation-state

- شريف يونس، نداء الشعب: تاريخ نقدي للأيديولوجيا الناصرية، الفصل الأول و الثاني، ص 37-196 (أرشف أيضا فصل "الزعامة"، ص 197-252)
- شريف يونس، "الزحف المقدس": مظاهرات التنحي وتشكل عبادة ناصر، فصل التنحي وانخاتم، ص 167-208
- Dalia Said Mostafa, *The Egyptian Military in Popular Culture: Context and Critique*, Chapter 2 and 3, p.23-92
- * Recommended: Barry B. Posen, "Nationalism, the Mass Army, and Military Power," *International Security*, Vol. 18, No. 2, Fall 1993, pp.80-124

Week Seven

Transformation of Egyptian identity under Sadat

From Economic Nationalism to *Infithah*; the soaring of identity politics

- Marie-Christine Aulas, "Sadat's Egypt: A Balance Sheet," *MERIP* 107: <http://www.merip.org/mer/mer107/sadats-egypt-balance-sheet>
- Relli Shechter, "The Cultural Economy of Development in Egypt: Economic Nationalism, Hidden Economy and the Emergence of Mass Consumer Society during Sadat's Infithah," *Middle Eastern Studies*, Vol. 44, No. 4, July 2008, pp.571-583

- Eric Davis, "[Ideology, Social Class, and Islamic Radicalism in Modern Egypt.](#)" *From Nationalism to Revolutionary Islam*, 1984
- شريف يونس، سؤال الهوية: الهوية و سلطة المثقف في عصر ما بعد الحداثة، الفصول 1 و 2 و 3، ص 17-108
- Walter Armbrust, *Mass Culture and Modernism in Egypt*, Chapters 1 and 2: p.1-36
- * Recommended: Hania Sobhy, "Secular Facade, Neoliberal Islamisation: Textbook Nationalism from Mubarak to Sisi," *Nations and Nationalism* 21 (4) 2015, pp.805-825

Week Eight

Spurts of revolutionary-democratic nationalism, overshadowed by authoritarian 'secular' and Islamic nationalisms: 1972/73 & 2011

- Ahmed Abdalla, *The Student Movement and National Politics in Egypt 1923-1973*, p.176-233
- شريف يونس، سؤال الهوية: الهوية و سلطة المثقف في عصر ما بعد الحداثة، فصل 8 "الحركة الطلابية في مصر في السبعينات"، ص 170-192
- *Recommended: Beinin, Joel. "Writing Class: Workers and Modern Egyptian Colloquial Poetry (Zajal)." *Poetics Today*, vol. 15, no. 2, 1994, pp. 191–215
- Dalia Said Mostafa, *The Egyptian Military in Popular Culture: Context and Critique*, Chapter 4, p.93-131
- Hesham Shafick, "The Fascist History of Egypt's revolution" I
<https://www.opendemocracy.net/arab-awakening/hesham-shafick/fascist-history-of-egypt-s-revolution>

Week Nine

Post-June 30; the triumph of chauvinism

- محمد نعيم، "أم الدنيا .. ضد الدنيا و خارجها" <https://almanassa.com/ar/story/1444>
- Amr Adly, "Egypt's Conservative Nationalism: Discourse and Praxis of the New Regime"
<http://carnegie-mec.org/2014/10/14/egypt-s-conservative-nationalism-discourse-and-praxis-of-new-regime-pub-56934>
- Sarah Carr, "From Nationalism to Resistance and Back Again"
<https://www.madamasr.com/en/2014/02/09/feature/culture/from-nationalism-to-resistance-and-back-again/>
- Egypt's Abdul Fattah al Sisi 'cult' sees surge in merchandise:
<http://www.bbc.com/news/world-middle-east-26775516>

Week Ten

Recap and Reflections

- Rogers Brubaker, "In the Name of the Nation: Reflections on Nationalism and Patriotism," *Citizenship Studies*, Vol. 8, No. 2, June 2004, pp.115-127